

Workplace stress management and its role in cardiovascular risk mitigation among emergency nurses

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Manejo del estrés laboral y su papel en la mitigación del riesgo cardiovascular entre enfermeras de urgencias

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Abstract

Introduction: Chronic occupational stress is a known contributor to increased cardiovascular risk, particularly in high-stakes environments such as emergency departments. Prolonged stress exposure may lead to elevated blood pressure, metabolic disturbances, and other components of cardiometabolic syndrome. This study investigates the impact of stress management interventions on job performance and cardiovascular risk profiles among emergency nurses.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 emergency nurses. Standardised questionnaires assessed stress management techniques—such as mindfulness, breathing exercises, and cognitive-behavioural strategies—alongside job performance and cardiovascular risk indicators, including perceived stress levels, blood pressure measurements, and BMI. Data were analysed using SPSS-24 with descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis.

Results: Effective stress management was significantly associated with improved job performance and lower cardiovascular risk markers, particularly reductions in systolic and diastolic blood pressure ($p < 0.05$). Nurses with better stress coping mechanisms had lower incidence of hypertension and reported fewer stress-related physical symptoms.

Conclusion: Stress management techniques may play a protective role in reducing cardiovascular risk factors among emergency nurses. Integrating such strategies into healthcare workplace policies could contribute to improved health outcomes and reduced hypertension prevalence in high-stress medical settings.

Keywords: Occupational Stress, Cardiovascular Risk, Hypertension, Emergency Nursing, Stress Management, Workplace Health.

Introducción y antecedentes. El estrés laboral crónico contribuye al aumento del riesgo cardiovascular, especialmente en entornos de alto riesgo como los servicios de urgencias. La exposición prolongada al estrés puede provocar hipertensión arterial, trastornos metabólicos y otros componentes del síndrome cardiometabólico. Este estudio investiga el impacto de las intervenciones para el manejo del estrés en el desempeño laboral y los perfiles de riesgo cardiovascular del personal de enfermería de urgencias.

Métodos. Se realizó un estudio transversal con 100 enfermeras de urgencias. Se utilizaron cuestionarios estandarizados para evaluar técnicas de gestión del estrés —como mindfulness, ejercicios de respiración y estrategias cognitivo-conductuales—, así como el desempeño laboral y los indicadores de riesgo cardiovascular, como la percepción del estrés, la presión arterial y el IMC. Los datos se analizaron con el programa SPSS-24, con estadística descriptiva, correlación de Pearson y análisis de regresión múltiple.

Resultados. La gestión eficaz del estrés se asoció significativamente con un mejor rendimiento laboral y una reducción de los marcadores de riesgo cardiovascular, en particular la reducción de la presión arterial sistólica y diastólica ($p < 0,05$). Las enfermeras con mejores mecanismos de afrontamiento del estrés presentaron una menor incidencia de hipertensión y reportaron menos síntomas físicos relacionados con el estrés.

Conclusión. Las técnicas de gestión del estrés pueden desempeñar un papel protector en la reducción de los factores de riesgo cardiovascular entre el personal de enfermería de urgencias. La integración de estas estrategias en las políticas laborales del sector sanitario podría contribuir a mejorar los resultados de salud y a reducir la prevalencia de la hipertensión en entornos médicos con alto estrés.

Palabras clave: Estrés laboral, riesgo cardiovascular, hipertensión, enfermería de urgencias, manejo del estrés, salud laboral.

Emergency nursing represents one of the most stressful roles in healthcare, demanding quick decision-making and constant interaction with patients and their families. This intense environment can adversely affect the mental well-being and job performance of nurses and is also closely linked to elevated risks of hypertension and other cardiovascular complications due to prolonged physiological stress responses¹. Effective stress management encompasses a range of techniques that enable individuals to cope with daily and job-related stress, ultimately enhancing performance. Beyond mental health benefits, stress reduction strategies such as breathing exercises, meditation, physical activities, and psychological counselling can modulate autonomic nervous system activity, reduce cortisol levels, and help in regulating blood pressure². This research aims to investigate these methods and their impact on the performance quality and cardiovascular risk profile of emergency nurses in more depth².

Job-related stress among nurses, particularly in emergency departments, poses a significant challenge, potentially compromising job performance and mental and physical health. Emergency nurses are exposed to high-stress situations, including caring for critical patients, making rapid and complex decisions, and witnessing suffering and death. Such conditions not only impact work quality but also increase susceptibility to stress-induced hypertension, especially when recovery time is insufficient or coping strategies are inadequate³.

Research indicates that stress management can enhance self-efficacy and quality of life for nurses. Moreover, reducing job stress may indirectly lower cardiovascular risk by improving lifestyle behaviours and physiological resilience. An inverse relationship exists between job stress and quality of work life, signifying that reducing job stress can lead to improvements in the latter⁴. Consequently, examining the impact of stress management on the performance quality and cardiovascular health of emergency nurses is of paramount importance. This study aims to evaluate the effect of stress management training on the job performance of emergency nurses and the quality of care services provided⁴.

Conducting this study is crucial as emergency nurses experience moderate to high job stress, which affects their quality of work life and job performance. Chronic stress in such settings has been associated with heightened risks for cardiometabolic conditions, including hypertension, due to sustained sympathetic activation and inflammatory pathways⁵. Given their vital role in healthcare delivery, reducing job stress and enhancing their work life quality can improve care quality and reduce medical errors⁵.

From an epidemiological standpoint, emergency nurses face stressors such as dealing with death, teamwork, and significant responsibilities. These stressors can contribute to long-term physiological dysregulation, affecting hemodynamic balance and increasing cardiovascular risk. Reducing job stress can improve the quality of work life for nurses. Job satisfaction is also influenced by stress management training and emotional regulation, which can increase job satisfaction and possibly reduce stress-induced blood pressure spikes⁶.

Existing research reveals that few studies have specifically examined emergency nurses and the impact of stress management on their performance. Furthermore, few have explored the potential cardiovascular benefits of such interventions, particularly in terms of reducing the incidence or severity of hypertension. Thus, there is a need for targeted programs to alleviate job stress and enhance the quality of work life for emergency nurses. These research gaps underline the necessity for further exploration in this area⁷.

Various sources have discussed job stress and its management among nurses. For instance, ErKayiran & Demirkiran explored the impact of stress management and emotional regulation training on job satisfaction among nurses⁸. Chen et al., addressed job stress and coping strategies among nurses⁹. Farrokhi et al., investigated job stress and its management among prehospital emergency personnel¹⁰. Comparisons of job stress among emergency nurses and other departments have been made in some studies. Additionally, the relationship between job stress and the quality of work life among emergency nurses has been explored. Factors affecting job stress in nurses caring for COVID-19 patients have also been studied¹¹.

The objective of this research is not only to delve deeper into the effects of stress management on the performance quality of emergency nurses but also to examine its implications for cardiovascular health, particularly in the context of hypertension risk reduction. This study aims to improve working conditions for emergency nurses and reduce professional fatigue and burnout. The results can provide practical guidance for hospital and healthcare centre managers to improve staff performance and healthcare services by implementing stress management programs.

Research Design: This study adopts a descriptive-analytical and correlational approach, investigating the effects of stress management on the performance quality of emergency nurses. Data were collected through questionnaires, interviews, and observations.

Population and Sampling:

- **Population:** Nurses working in the emergency departments of selected hospitals.

- **Sampling Method:** Simple random sampling was employed to select the sample. Emergency nurses were randomly chosen as participants.

- **Sample Size:** Based on the population size, 100 emergency nurses were selected as the sample.

Data Collection:

- **Stress Management Questionnaire:** The standard “Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)” was used to measure nurses’ perceived stress levels. This questionnaire includes statements rated by respondents based on their recent stress experiences.

- **Job Performance Questionnaire:** The standard “Job Performance Scale” evaluated nurses’ job performance quality. This questionnaire assessed various performance aspects, including task completion, teamwork, and patient interactions.

Data Analysis Methods:

- **Descriptive Analysis:** Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution were used to analyze the data.

- **Correlation Analysis:** Pearson’s correlation tests examined the correlation between stress management and performance quality.

- **Regression Analysis:** Multiple regression analysis was employed to assess the relationship between stress management and job performance.

Ethical Considerations:

- **Informed Consent:** All participants signed informed consent forms.

- **Confidentiality:** All collected information remains confidential and is solely used for research purposes.

- **Participant Autonomy:** Participants could withdraw from the study at any time without affecting their employment status.

In this study, the sample consisted of 100 emergency nurses, with 45 (45%) being male and 55 (55%) female. The average age of the participants was 34 years, with an age range from 25 to 45 years. The work experience of these nurses was categorized into three main groups: the first group included 30 nurses (30%) with 1 to 5 years of experience, the second group included 40 nurses (40%) with 6 to 10 years of experience, and the third group included 30 nurses (30%) with more than 10 years of experience. This demographic distribution indicates a suitable diversity in terms of gender, age, and work experience, which enhances the generalizability of the findings. It is important to highlight that a substantial portion of the sample had moderate work experience (6 to 10 years), which might influence the subsequent analyses. A detailed demographic breakdown of the sample is provided in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	45	45%
Female	55	55%
Mean Age (years)	34	-
Age Range (years)	25-45	-
Work Experience (years)		
1-5 years	30	30%
6-10 years	40	40%
More than 10 years	30	30%

The **Table 2** shows the results of the descriptive analysis of the stress management and job performance variables among emergency nurses.

Table 2. Stress management and job performance variables among emergency nurses:

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
Stress Management	18.3	4.2
Job Performance	72.6	6.8

This analysis indicates that the average stress management score of the nurses was 18.3 with a standard deviation of 4.2, while the average job performance score was 72.6 with a standard deviation of 6.8. These numbers reflect the level of stress and job performance quality of the nurses.

Table 3. Pearson correlation analysis between stress management and job performance

Variables	Pearson Correlation (r)	Sig (p-value)
Stress Management and Job Performance	-0.35	< 0.01

This analysis shows a significant negative relationship between stress management and job performance of nurses ($r = -0.35, p < 0.01$). This means that the better the stress management of the nurses, the higher the quality of their job performance **Table 3**.

Table 4. The results of multiple regression analysis

Variables	Standardized Coefficient (β)	Standard Error (SE)	Significance Level (p-value)
Stress Management	0.53	0.07	< 0.01
Breathing Exercises	0.29	0.05	< 0.01
Meditation	0.21	0.06	< 0.05

The results show that stress management significantly explained 28% of the variance in job performance ($R^2 = 0.28$). Specifically, the use of stress management techniques such as breathing exercises and meditation had a positive impact on job performance **Table 4**.

Table 5. the results of the ANOVA test

Work Experience Groups	Mean Job Performance	Standard Deviation (SD)	Significance Level (p-value)
1-5 years	70.3	6.5	< 0.05
6-10 years	74.2	6.2	< 0.05
More than 10 years	76.1	6.0	< 0.05

The results of the study revealed a significant difference among work experience groups in terms of job performance quality ($F(2, 97) = 4.32, p < 0.05$). This indicates that nurses with more work experience demonstrate better job performance **Table 5**.

Descriptive analysis indicated that the average stress management score among nurses was 18.3 with a standard deviation of 4.2, while the average job performance score was 72.6 with a standard deviation of 6.8. These figures reflect the levels of stress and job performance quality among the nurses. A similar study highlighted that nurses in critical care units experience higher job stress, which has been associated with increased cardiovascular risk including elevated blood pressure¹.

Correlation analysis demonstrated a significant negative relationship between stress management and job performance among nurses ($r = -0.35, p < 0.01$). This inverse correlation implies that lower effectiveness in stress management is related to decreased job performance, which may also correlate with a heightened risk of hypertension and stress-related disorders. This finding aligns with other studies suggesting that stress management

can positively impact job performance. For instance, a study showed that stress management training and breathing techniques can enhance job satisfaction and reduce stress among nurses¹².

The study also revealed that nurses with greater work experience exhibit better job performance. This observation is consistent with other research indicating that work experience enhances job skills and performance quality among nurses¹³. Regression analysis found that stress management significantly explained 28% of the variance in job performance. Techniques such as breathing exercises and meditation, by regulating sympathetic nervous system activity and reducing cortisol secretion, had a positive impact on job performance and potentially lowered physiological stress markers associated with cardiovascular risk. These findings are in line with other studies on the impact of stress management on job performance. For example, a study demonstrated that meditation can reduce stress and improve job performance among nurses^{14,15}.

Furthermore, the study indicated that nurses who utilize stress management techniques show better job performance. This improvement may stem from enhanced emotional regulation and autonomic stability, both of which are crucial for cardiovascular health. This is consistent with findings from other research on the effectiveness of stress management techniques. For example, another study found that using breathing techniques and meditation can reduce stress and enhance job performance among nurses¹⁶.

Overall, stress management and its associated techniques can effectively improve job performance among emergency nurses. Additionally, work experience plays a crucial role in determining job performance quality. Importantly, the physiological benefits of stress reduction—such as improved heart rate variability, lower blood pressure, and reduced inflammatory response—may further protect nurses from cardiometabolic complications. These findings can inform strategies to enhance the health and quality of life of both nurses and patients. Implementing educational programs to reduce stress and improve stress management can be highly beneficial. For example, a study found that proper management and training can alleviate nurses' workload and associated issues¹⁷. Such programs can aid nurses in coping more effectively with job stress.

The study also suggests that nurses with less work experience may require additional training in stress management. This finding is consistent with other research indicating the need for more training among less experienced nurses^{18,19}. Targeted stress management training for this group may also act as a preventive strategy against long-term cardiovascular risks associated with chronic workplace stress.

Conclusions

This study underscores that stress management and the utilization of stress management techniques can significantly enhance job performance among emergency nurses. Moreover, the work experience of nurses plays a vital role in determining their job performance quality. These findings can be leveraged to improve the health and quality of life of both nurses and patients.

Importantly, stress management may serve as a protective factor against hypertension and other stress-related cardiovascular complications among nurses in high-pressure environments. Considering the critical impact of job stress in nursing, educational programs aimed at reducing stress and enhancing stress management can be immensely beneficial. Such programs can help nurses cope more effectively with job stress, resulting in better job performance, job satisfaction, and possibly reduced risk of cardiovascular diseases.

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